

.INSTRUCTIONAL METHODOLOGY AND TEACHING PROCEDURES: A GUIDE FOR TEACHERS IN TRAINING

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Introduction

Instructional methodology is a set of principles that a teacher uses to impart knowledge on learners based on the content, level of learners and materials used in teaching and learning. It is crucial and the particular ways of presenting instruction in teaching and learning situations, which is necessary to develop a design for an instructional system. A teacher in training should be able to select a particular method based on the subject matter, level of learners and the kind of instructional resources that would be applied in teaching for effective learning. It is also important for would be teacher to select methods that would ensure the assessment of the content, resources and the level of achievement.

Paper Objectives

- i. define teaching methodology
- ii. describe various instructional methods based on the content to be taught and the level of learners.
- iii. list and explain various methods, their strengths and weaknesses
- iv. identify the procedures for selecting instructional methods

Instructional Methodology

Teaching methods are of various kinds: human, cultural, natural and scientific. The teacher is as effective as his/her tools of teaching and impacting knowledge and skills. However, teaching methods are often concerned with facilitated learning or instructional resources/materials. That is, things and people that can help us to learn, including technology.

Why do we need to use instructional resources/materials in facilitating the learning process? We can adapt or use instructional resources/materials (electronic or non-electronic) to achieve the following:

1. Save time and energy
 2. Make learning permanent, real and immediate
 3. Make learning interesting
 4. Motivate learners
 5. Make learning authentic
 6. Bring what is not in the immediate environment to the class and
 7. Make learning effective and impressionable
- Methods offer general guideline on the purpose of teaching the content.

Teaching techniques are the specific means by which those general objectives are accomplished. However, educationist must always keep it in mind that out of the numerous methods available, which one(s) would be the most successful in handling a particular topic and the instructional resources to be used (Alhassan & Adeoye, 2006). Teachers in training are in the art of teaching in order to assist their learners. In teaching, the concern of the teacher is how to make students learn. If any teacher wants to teach, knowing the subject matter is not enough, he or she should be able to study the learners, and know the appropriate method to be employed in order to encourage efficient and effective teaching and learning.

The skilful and proficient teacher has the ability to use both verbal and non-verbal responses to draw the attention of the learners in asking the right type of questions necessary for the purpose of achieving the stated objectives in order to reinforce the desirable behaviours. Meanwhile, no method is absolutely perfect when used in the classroom. A teacher can make use of more than one method that are appropriate for a particular topic. For instance, in a language class, a teacher should teach grammar by using grammar translation method and communicative language method in order to make teaching and learning interactive (Ishola, 2017).

Various Instructional Methods that Can be Used at the Basic Level

The following teaching methods can be easily used in teaching most of the subjects taught at the basic level since NCE teachers are prepared to teach at the basic level of education in Nigeria (FRN, 2013).

- i. Story telling methods
- ii. Play away
- iii. Dramatisation and role playing
- iv. Discovery method
- v. Project method

Story Telling Method

This method has been employed at the lower level of education. In African traditional education, story-telling was the most efficient and effective way to teach historical concepts as well as religious and moral education. The method is similar to lecture method which is common in higher level of institution except that the approach differs in principles.

Strengths of Story Telling Method

1. Unlike lecture method, there is no boredom or fatigue in the classroom as learners sit together listening to the teacher telling some interesting stories with illustration on the use of appropriate instructional material such as picture, posters, etc.
2. It makes young and adult learn in a related and entertaining manner.
3. It is appropriate in teaching arts and humanity related subjects such as Religious Studies, History, Social Studies, among others.

Weaknesses of Story Telling Method

1. This method makes learners perceive because they may not be so much involve in the learning activity.
2. Things to be done should look natural to real life situation, not to be forced or forged to create doubts.
3. The method is also criticised for not emphasising the intellectual and practical involvement of the learners.

Play Away Method

This method is free and spontaneous as the learning should be communicated in an interesting manner. The method is useful in science related subjects with the recognition of various teaching resources/materials.

The advocate of the method (Montessori) emphasised that learners should be active involve in what to learn as they are free to explore various activities that would make them learn. This method is mostly useful at the primary school level.

Strength of Play Away Method

1. It develops the innate ability of the learners
2. It builds confidence in the learners and encourages cooperation within play group.
3. It is easy for the teacher to make on the spot assessment of learning activities.

Weaknesses of Play Away Method

1. If not properly handled, learning objectives may not be achieved as learners may disrupt the learning activities.
2. It is time consuming as various activities would be engaged in with limited time.
3. Classroom management may not be achieved because learners have to move from one location to another within the classroom.

Dramatisation and Role Playing Method

Dramatisation is technique used by the learners in school to change facts or skills to be learnt into drama in order to make learning more interesting. In this way, learners are to dramatise short stories, scenes and passages. In dramatisation, each learner will be assigned specific role to play with an attempt to make situation clear to them. Its purpose is to help learners see a situation through other learners' point of view. This method is most useful in language and literature subjects, Music, Physical and Health Education, among others.

Strengths of Dramatisation and Role Playing Method

1. It provides learners with a system of communication that is based on actions rather than expressions.

2. It also provides techniques for analysing problems which involve human factors or items of interpersonal.
3. It enables a group of learners the skills to pretest ideas that may have significance for the future.

Weaknesses of Dramatisation and Role Playing Method

1. The method is time consuming. If properly done, it takes at least an hour of highly concentrated activity.
2. The method may demand some preparation on the part of learners.
3. It may not be successful if learners are not actively engaged in the role assigned to them.

Discovery Method

This is a teaching method that avoids instruction but encourages learners to find out things for themselves. It also seeks to train learners in the techniques of how to obtain information that they need. Discovery method, according to Abimbola (2009), is a problem solving approach. This method is appropriate in vocational and technical education subjects such as Fine and Apply Arts, Wood Work, Home Economics, among others.

Strengths of Discovery Method

1. It is capable of application to a wide range of learning.
2. It promotes flexible investigation and cultural responses to solving problems.
3. It promotes learners' awareness and curiosity in learning new things.

Weaknesses of Discovery Method

1. It makes teacher a mere guide and adviser to the learners.
2. It requires a lot of thought and planning.
3. It also requires a lot of patience as guess, trail and errors are manifested.

Project Method

This is in form of research in higher institution as it takes the form of thesis but at the lower level of education, it could be different group of learners in accomplishing a given task. In Agriculture Science class for instance, learners may be grouped to cultivate a piece of land.

Strengths of Project Method

1. It is done in a relaxed mood since it takes a considerable period of time.
2. It encourages individual learners to work at their own pace.
3. It allows learners to be creative and brings out innate ability of individual learners.

Weaknesses of Project Methods

1. It is too demanding for the teachers because such a teacher may need to guide learners at each point which could be frustrating.
2. It is time consuming and may affect normal classroom activities.
3. At times, it is difficult to coordinate because some learners might be lazy.

Procedure for Selecting Instructional Methods

The level of conceptualisation and organisation within a method is referred to as procedure (Richards and Rodgers, 2001). This encompasses the actual moment-to-moment techniques, practices, and behaviours that operate in teaching according to a particular method. It is the level at which we describe how a method realises its approach and design in classroom behaviour. At the level of design we saw that a method will advocate the use of certain types of teaching activities as a consequence of its theoretical assumptions about learning. There are three dimensions to a method at the level of procedure according to Richards and Rodgers (2001) which are:

- a. the use of teaching activities (drills, dialogues, information-gap activities, etc.) to present new concept and to clarify and demonstrate formal, communicative or other aspects of learning;
- b. the ways in which particular teaching activities are used for teaching; and
- c. the procedures and techniques used in giving feedback to learners concerning the form or content of instruction.

More so, the level of learners, their age, environment, learners' need and the type of assessment that will bring out appropriate feedback are the procedure to be followed in selecting instructional methods to teach in the classroom situation.

Conclusion

What is worth doing at all is worth doing well. Why doing a thing if you will not be proud of doing it or known for it? This statement is suitable for the teaching profession nowadays. In order to be known as a good teacher, you must be effective. Effectiveness in the teaching profession requires adequate preparation for the classroom delivery. To be a good teacher, you must know when to act, react and interact with the learners using appropriate methods and adequate instructional resources. In this chapter however, we are able to discuss teaching methodology, various instructional methods based on the content to be taught and the level of learners, explanation of various methods, their strengths and weaknesses, and the procedures for selecting instructional methods. Though, there are various instructional methods, a dedicated teacher should be able to select appropriate ones based on the procedures for teaching and learning to be successful.

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